

The CAELUM Methodology: a unified approach to crisis management across different library contexts

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Partnership

	Name	Logo
1	University of Tartu	
2	Web2Learn	
3	Kaunas University of Technology	
4	Ukrainian State University of Science and Technologies	
5	SKS Knowledge Services	

Revision History

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List of Abbreviations

The following table presents the acronyms used in the deliverable in alphabetical order.

Abbreviations	Description
EU	European Union
HE	Higher Education
UA	Ukraine
WP	Work package

Executive Summary

The CAELUM Methodology develops a unified approach to crisis management across different library contexts, building on the insights gained from previous activities (WP2A1 and WP2A2) in the framework of the project and broadening the scope with a wider literature review on the roles of libraries during different kinds of crises. It begins with a background analysis of the roles of libraries during crises and the presentation of the case studies that each partner will implement in Work Package (WP) 3. It continues with the development of the unified approach by identifying 5 library roles in crisis management. Each role is described in a theoretical framework, is connected with specific types of crises and is related with references and practical tools that support each role.

Then, the report lists some indicative conceptual tools for exploring the expectations and needs of the groups engaged in each case study of the WP3 and the barriers and gaps that libraries may face in responding to crises. In addition, some target audience engagement methods are mentioned based on the literature review. Both the conceptual tools and the audience engagement methods are non-exhaustive ones. The aim of this Methodology is to serve as a guide to libraries for consistent and effective crisis response and as a unified approach for the implementation of the pilot cases in WP3.

About CAELUM

CAELUM (Open science supporting vulnerable communities: empowering university libraries in crisis response, 2025-2027, <https://caelum.ut.ee/>) is a 2-year Erasmus+ project that places university libraries in the forefront of crisis response through open science, supporting vulnerable communities and bolstering EU-UA cooperation. Through a series of activities, CAELUM aims to upskill university libraries' staff in innovative and interdisciplinary approaches to crisis response and promote and sustain university libraries-driven open knowledge and civic engagement among HE students and staff for crisis response. Thus, CAELUM empowers university libraries in leveraging open and citizen science approaches as well as community engagement practices for crisis response in multiple contexts.

1. Introduction: The role of libraries in crises

In recent years, the international scene has confronted different kinds of crises that seem to be a frequent phenomenon. Climate change, economic crises, authoritarianism, populism, wars and the Covid-19 pandemic are just some of the crises that have threatened human existence and its well-being as well as the planet (Kushnir, et al., p. 14)¹. In this context, libraries' role during a crisis is inseparably connected with their role in the communities. According to Laurian et al. (2025) "local public libraries are essential community assets. Above and beyond their collections, information access, and literacy-oriented programming, libraries assist communities in a multitude of ways: by providing free, open, and welcoming spaces for all; by supporting patrons' job searches and applications; by acting as government document repositories, cooling and warming centers, and gathering spaces for civic organizations, seniors, youth, and teenagers; by providing food to children; and, during the COVID-19 pandemic, by creatively redesigning their services to support their patrons' information needs and, for some, by acting as testing and vaccination centers"².

Hence, libraries' role in the communities seem to adapt to the socioeconomic, environmental and political context, especially in times of uncertainty and doubt. The social role of an inclusive library in a community-centered perspective is underscored by Chancellor (2017): "The library as a physical space that remains open for all members of the community in times of crisis reflects a broader understanding of the library as protecting equal access and fulfilling social responsibility."³

This Methodology is the deliverable of activity 4 of the WP2 that is dedicated to develop a unified crisis management methodology for academic libraries across different crises contexts. It will serve as a guide for consistent and effective crisis response and will be tailored to diverse library contexts. The CAELUM methodology builds on the insights gained from the previous activities, namely:

- WP2A1, a comprehensive resource collection that explores the role of libraries during crises. This collection involves 40 resources, from practical strategies to theoretical frameworks, offering insights into the evolving

¹ Kushnir, I. and Yazgan, N. (2024). Conceptualising the International Phenomenon of Crises. Kushnir, I., Sood, K., Park, M.S.-A., Zhong, H. and Serret, N. (Ed.) Education and Sustainable Development in the Context of Crises: International Case Studies of Transformational Change. Emerald Publishing Limited. Leeds. pp. 9–21. p. 14. <https://doi.org/10.1108/978-1-83797-773-420241002>

² Laurian, L., Doyle, E., Vamanu, I., & Logsdon, K. (2024). Libraries Are Resilience Hubs: Evidence From the Midwest. *Journal of the American Planning Association*, 91(1), 58–71. p.1. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01944363.2024.2343670>

³ Chancellor, R. L. (2017). Libraries As Pivotal Community Spaces in Times of Crisis. *Urban Library Journal*, 23 (1). p. 6. Retrieved from <https://academicworks.cuny.edu/ulj/vol23/iss1/2>

roles of libraries in times of multiple kinds of crises. All CAELUM partners contributed to the collection of the resources that refer to initiatives at international, European and national level and are available at the CAELUM website [here](#).

- WP2A2, national reports on the results of the focus group discussions and surveys implemented at national level based on commonly agreed corpus of research questions at consortium's level⁴. These insightful reports captured diverse perspectives on library's roles in crises based on the experiences and the opinions of the participants (mainly library's staff, academics and students) and revealed practices, challenges, and opportunities for civic engagement through university libraries.

Beyond the above-mentioned insights, this methodology is based also on a wider literature review of the role of libraries in crises. For the needs of the WP2A2, the consortium has decided to define the notion of crisis as per below: "a crisis is a time of great danger, difficulty or doubt when problems must be solved, or important decisions must be made ([Oxford Learner's Dictionaries](#)). This can include experiences such as a global pandemic, war or armed conflict, political turbulence, economic hardship, climate-related emergencies, or information-related challenges like disinformation or information overload."

Therefore, the present Methodology aims to develop a unified approach to crisis management, by navigating to the different roles that libraries may undertake in the context of various crises, and thus contributing to consistent and effective crisis response.

2. Scope of the Methodology

The Methodology aims to systematise the different roles that libraries may undertake in the context of different types of crises and thus, presenting a unified crisis management approach for libraries. To achieve this goal, it refers to insights from previous CAELUM deliverables (namely WP2A1, collection of resources and WP2A2, national reports on the results of the focus group discussions and surveys) but also to wider literature review regarding the roles of libraries in diverse types of crises. The CAELUM Methodology directly contributes to the general project objective of enhancing the crisis response capacities of libraries for the benefit of vulnerable communities by developing a unified approach in guiding libraries on how to effectively respond to and manage crises through civic engagement.

Thus, the Methodology will pave the way for the next project's activity, WP2A5, a set of 5 tailored action plans, one from each partner organisation, that will demonstrate how to

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/communities/caelum/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

apply the CAELUM methodology in diverse contexts, showcasing practical steps and strategies for libraries to effectively function as community hubs in crisis response. The CAELUM Methodology (WP2A4) along with the action plans (WP2A5) will guide the implementation of CAELUM case studies (WP3A2). Activity 2 involves the practical application of the CAELUM methodology in real-world scenarios as each partner will undertake a unique case study, addressing diverse crises.

The main themes of CAELUM cases studies per partner are described briefly below:

1. **University of Tartu** will implement a case study on the library's role in student well-being;
2. **Web2Learn** will implement a case study on enhancing library's services for disabled citizens;
3. **Kaunas University of Technology** will implement a case study on tackling the integration and unemployment of foreign students;
4. **Ukrainian State University of Science and Technologies** will implement a case study on combating disinformation during crises;
5. **SKS Knowledge Services** will implement a case study on a citizen science approach to crisis research.

The titles of the case studies are depicted in the following figure.

Made with Napkin

Figure 1 CAELUM cases studies per partner

3. Libraries roles for societal resilience during crisis

We have identified 5 roles for libraries during crises based on the insights of previous project's activities and literature review. These roles have been outlined in a previous CAELUM result (cf. the A1 typology, which is mainly a bottom-up typology designed by the CAELUM partnership with the contribution of all partners, backed by the A1 literature review).

The identified roles are:

- Role 1: Libraries as community hubs [R1]
- Role 2: Libraries as resilience hubs [R2]
- Role 3: Libraries as lifelong learning hubs for both patrons and library's staff [R3]
- Role 4: Libraries as places that foster social and digital inclusion [R4]
- Role 5: Libraries as flexible, multi-use spaces [R5]

Each role is related to specific types of crisis and each role is analysed based on the following items:

- Scope;
- Question;
- References;
- Activities/tools.

The scope gives the outline of each role, while the question asks for the features that would contribute to transforming the role of the library in the specific one. Finally, the references cite the bibliographic references that are relevant to each role and the disposition/tools analyse the practical tools or means that would contribute to the realisation of the specific role. Each bibliographic reference on the item "References" is connected to a specific tool in the item "Disposition/tools" by numbering each reference and matching it with a specific tool.

3.1. Role 1: Libraries as community hubs [R1]

This role is more relevant to crises related to conflicts or war and its consequences (refugees, exiled).

Scope	Libraries serve as community hubs where people meet, feel safe and exchange ideas and experiences in times of crisis.
Question	How could libraries be transformed into community hubs?
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Grinchenko University Library. (March 11, 2025). The Living Library Project: Meeting with Warrior Oleksiy Lukyanets. Retrieved in Ukrainian from: https://library.kubg.edu.ua/pro-biblioteku/podii-ta-novyny/682-projekt-zhyva-biblioteka-zustrich-z-voinom-oleksiiem-lukiantsem.html [R1.1] • Rampen, J. (2017). Good deeds: the mobile library reaching refugees' hearts and minds. The Guardian. Retrieved

	<p>from: https://www.theguardian.com/books/2020/mar/10/echo-mobile-library-greece-refugee-camps [R1.2]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chancellor, R. L. (2017). Libraries As Pivotal Community Spaces in Times of Crisis. <i>Urban Library Journal</i>, 23 (1). Retrieved from: https://academicworks.cuny.edu/ulj/vol23/iss1/2 [R1.3] Cigarini, A., Bonhoure, I., Vicens, J., Perelló, J. (2021). Public libraries embrace citizen science: Strengths and challenges. <i>Library & Information Science Research</i>. Volume 43. Issue 2. 101090. ISSN 0740-8188. https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lisr.2021.101090 [R1.4] Seed Libraries: Building Community, Resilience and Seed Security (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jBSJpPOZDi4) [R1.5]
Activities/tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organisation of events and workshops that give voice to people affected directly by a conflict (ex. warriors) [R1.1] Mobile libraries that reach vulnerable communities [R1.2] Calm and safe places [R1.3] Implementation of Citizen Science projects (connected with local problems or concerns) [R1.4] Creation of seed libraries that foster food security [R1.5]

3.2. Role 2: Libraries as resilience hubs [R2]

This role is more relevant to crises related to armed conflicts and environment-related emergencies.

Scope	Libraries undertake a central role in periods of armed conflicts and climate-related emergencies
Question	How could libraries be transformed into resilience hubs?
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lyons, D. (2025). Lessons in Resilience: Libraries' Roles in Disaster Preparedness and Recovery <i>Climate Crisis</i>. <i>Library Journal</i>. Retrieved from: https://www.libraryjournal.com/story/lessons-in-resilience-libraries-roles-in-disaster-preparedness-and-recover [R2.1] Laurian, L., Doyle, E., Vamanu, I., & Logsdon, K. (2024). Libraries Are Resilience Hubs: Evidence From the Midwest.

	<p>Journal of the American Planning Association, 91(1), 58–71. https://doi.org/10.1080/01944363.2024.2343670 [R2.2]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jonaitytė, L., Štuopytė, E., Tautkevičienė, G., (2024). Academic libraries as niches of social cohesion. AGILE consortium. [R2.3] • Bezzub I., & Bezzub Y. (2024). The Role of Libraries in Covering Ecocide in Ukraine Caused by Russian Aggression, 71, pp. 383 – 397. https://doi.org/10.15407/np.71.383 [R2.4] • Ecocide in Ukraine during the Russian-Ukrainian War: Recommended Bibliographic List of Literature / Kyiv National University Scientific Library; [compiled by Koshlyakova, N. V.; under general editorship of Tishchenko, I. I.]; Kyiv: [publisher not specified], 2023. [R2.5]
<p>Activities/tools</p>	<p><u>During crisis:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Libraries as shelters during conflicts or severe weather conditions (use computers, power up a device (charging stations), or just stay warm) [R2.1 & R2.3] • Libraries as disaster response centers [R2.1] • Libraries as a humanitarian and crisis management hub [R2.3] • Libraries a center of communication and information point for the community [R2.1 & R2.3] • Libraries to disseminate information on website, social media accounts [R2.1] • Dissemination of calls for help/support/materials in social media accounts [R2.1] • Libraries as key climate resiliency partners with local authorities [R2.1] • Libraries as testing and vaccination centers (during COVID era) [R2.2] <p><u>After crisis (recovery phase):</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of help to fill out state-aid forms for allowances [R2.1] • Organisation of workshops for staff for disaster preparedness and recovery efforts [R2.1 & R2.2]

3.3. Role 3: Libraries as lifelong learning hubs [R3]

This role is more relevant to crises related to unemployment, discrimination resulting from disability and challenges related to open science.

<p>Scope</p>	<p>Libraries are considered trustworthy knowledge institutions that can expand their traditional service of lending books to lifelong learning services addressing different types of crises: unemployment and</p>
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	<p>challenges related to open science. One of the pillars of open science is open educational resources (OER). It is OER that enables the continuity of learning without barriers and the implementation of education throughout life. University libraries in many countries are actively involved in the advocacy, creation, adaptation, dissemination of OER.</p>
Question	How could libraries be transformed into lifelong learning hubs?
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bibliothèque publique d'information Centre Pompidou: You are a job seeker. Retrieved from: https://www.bpi.fr/en/practical-information/offers-by-type-of-visitor/job-seeker/ [R3.1] • Drexel University Library, Career exploration and planning Retrieved from: https://libguides.library.drexel.edu/c.php?g=176932&p=1163396 [R3.2] • Hunter, C. (2021). How can academic libraries help support students' mental health?. Reflective Professional, 1. https://doi.org/10.48525/rp-2021-id130 [R3.3] • Libraries Ireland: Employment Support website. Retrieved from: https://www.librariesireland.ie/employment-support?utm_source [R3.4] • The City College of New York. Accessibility Resources & Services: Staff Training & Resources. Retrieved from: https://library.cuny.cuny.edu/c.php?g=535291&p=5691402 [R3.5] • Kolesnykova, T. (2023). Year of sustainability, openness, and new roles: A Ukrainian university library in wartime. Problems and Perspectives in Management, 21(2-si), 114-122. doi:10.21511/ppm.21(2-si).2023.14 • Kolesnykova, T. (2023). Open educational resources and open textbooks in the context of strengthening the leadership potential of higher education libraries in knowledge accessibility. 7, 3-15. DOI: https://doi.org/10.36273/2076-9555.2023.7(324).3-15 • Open Educational Resources : Common Repository of the University of Science and Technologies. (n. d). The institutional repository of the Ukrainian State University of Science and Technologies https://crust.ust.edu.ua/communities/7c46470b-db9b-42c3-8771-298386ce9fd7/search
Activities/tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self training spaces dedicated to lifelong independent learning (learning of a language, office software, the highway code) [R3.1]

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshops and lectures for acquiring new skills [R3.1] • Online resources for learning new skills and new languages [R3.1, R3.2 & R3.4] • E-books and audio books for advice in career changing [R3.4] • Upskilling for librarians: continuous training (workshops, webinars, conferences) and professional development of staff in new technologies, customer service. [R3.3] • Provision of Qualified Training (The Mental Health First Aid (MHFA) Qualification) [R3.3] • Collection of online training for library's staff on disabilities [R3.5]
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3.4. Role 4: Libraries as places that foster social and digital inclusion [R4]

This role is more relevant to crises related to well-being, discrimination resulting from disability and free access to information.

Scope	Libraries are welcoming places for people suffering from loneliness and isolation and offer free access to information (countering disinformation), to the internet and technological devices (computers, tablets, and e-readers).
Question	How could libraries foster digital and social inclusion?
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kish, I., Thominet, H., Zignani, T. How can the EU leverage the potential of public libraries to tackle European challenges? Libraries on the European Agenda. Urban Agenda for the EU. Retrieved from: https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2021-05/ACTION%205%20-%20Libraries%20on%20the%20European%20Agenda%20-%20PL%202030_Final_O.pdf [R4.1] • Panteion University Library: Support for people with disabilities. Retrieved from: https://library.panteion.gr/en/services/services-for-disabled-people/ [R4.2] • Nudyshchuk, G., & Horban, Y. (2025). Public libraries of Ukraine as entities of information security in the context of the Russian-Ukrainian war. Collection of Scientific Papers ΛΟΓΟΣ. (December 13, 2024; Zurich, Switzerland). 409–412. https://doi.org/10.36074/logos-13.12.2024.088 [R4.3] • Willingham, T. L. (2008). Libraries as civic agents. Public Library Quarterly, 27(2), 97–110 [R4.4]

Activities/tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of digital lending services, allowing users to borrow eBooks and audiobooks remotely [R4.1] • Implementation of technology training programs to help patrons develop digital literacy skills [R4.1] • Leverage of technology to enhance user experience and offer assistive technology software for disabled users [R4.2] • Provision of access to trustworthy information in turbulent periods (countering disinformation and propaganda) [R4.3] • Organising communities of interest (ex. writing workshops, book discussions, exhibitions of work by local artists) aiming at different groups of community members [R4.4] • Organising virtual international events for war-displaced citizens
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3.5. Role 5: Libraries as flexible, multi-use spaces [R5]

This role is more relevant to crises related with mental health/well-being issues and discrimination that is connected to disability.

Scope	Libraries are open spaces that welcome patrons from all walks of life in an inclusive way that promote mental health and well being.
Question	What kind of spaces should a library entail in its premises?
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nance, M. K. (2022). Playing for Keeps: How academic libraries are prioritizing student mental health and well-being through play. <i>The Journal of Play in Adulthood</i> 4(2). 162-176. doi: https://doi.org/10.5920/jpa.1026 [R5.1] • Hunter C. (2021). How can academic libraries help support students' mental health?. <i>Reflective Professional</i>, 1. https://doi.org/10.48525/rp-2021-id130 [R5.2] • University of Bath. Support for students and staff with disabilities: Sensory room. Retrieved from: https://library.bath.ac.uk/library-services-for-users-with-disabilities/sensory-room [R5.3] • Eugenides Foundation. Workstations in the library for disabled users. Retrieved from: https://www.eef.edu.gr/en/visit/accessibility/in-the-library/ [R5.4]
Activities/tools	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meditation/relaxation room [R5.1 & R5.2] • Quiet zones [R5.3] • Dimmed spaces for light sensitivity [R5.3] • Accessible workstations/Assistive technology rooms [R5.4]

4. Conceptual tools for action plans

Each partner, depending on the type of crises that tackles in the relevant cases studies (WP3A2) should define the conceptual tools for exploring the expectations and needs of students, academic staff, library's professionals and other groups engaged in each case study regarding library's support in crisis situations. The same applies for exploring the barriers and gaps that libraries may face in responding to crises. Some conceptual tools identified in the literature review are listed below:

- Data collection (focus groups discussions, interviews and questionnaires in the form of a survey)⁵;
- Online (anonymous) feedback form⁶ for collecting users' feedback; and
- Usability testing⁷. This tool involves users performing specific tasks while observers note difficulties and gather feedback. This method assesses the effectiveness and user-friendliness of library's systems and interfaces, guiding improvements in digital and physical services.

The above-mentioned conceptual tools are non-exhaustive, and it is advisable for each partner to adjust these tools or other tools to the specific needs of the case study that will be implemented based on the case-specific library context. Partners should consider existing resources such as budget, personnel, and available facilities when selecting tools and formulating action plans. This approach ensures that the plans developed are realistic and feasible within the given constraints.

⁵ Hunter C. (2021). How can academic libraries help support students' mental health?. *Reflective Professional*, 1. <https://doi.org/10.48525/rp-2021-id130>. p. 9-11.

⁶ University of Oulu. Accessible library services. Retrieved from: <https://oulu.finna.fi/Feedback/Form/FeedbackService?lng=en-gb>

⁷ The National Library of Greece collaborates with the NPO "Me Alla Matia". Retrieved in Greek from: <https://meallamatia.services/blog/2022/11/11/%CE%B7-%CE%B5%CE%B8%CE%BD%CE%B9%CE%BA%CE%AE-%CE%B2%CE%B9%CE%B2%CE%BB%CE%B9%CE%BF%CE%B8%CE%AE%CE%BA%CE%B7-%CE%B5%CE%BB%CE%BB%CE%AC%CE%B4%CE%BF%CF%82-%CE%BC%CE%B5-%CE%AC%CE%BB%CE%BB%CE%B1/>

5. Target audience engagement

In the era of the digital revolution, libraries face the challenge to remain relevant to the users' needs and expectations and at the same time, make their services visible and known to the public, by developing audience engagement practices⁸. A key finding from the Greek report on focus group discussion and survey results on the role of libraries during crises⁹ indicated that there is a general lack of knowledge about library's services among potential users and subsequently in a period of crisis, users usually lack the knowledge of the services that the libraries could provide as they have no previous experience in using them. Hence, although there are no specific methods for audience engagement during a crisis, we list some practices for audience engagement based on the wider literature review as the trust to the library is important to have been established before a crisis arises. If citizens have no previous engagement with a library, it is less possible to approach it during a crisis, when uncertainty and doubt prevail.

Here is a list of target audience engagement methods:

- meditation sessions with the collaboration of a psychologist that involve different relaxation techniques (ex. breathing exercises, guided visualization, mindfulness exercises);¹⁰
- art therapy sessions (ex. drawing with colors);¹¹
- discussion sessions in an informal environment based on films screening with a crisis-relevant theme;¹²
- art events (ex. exhibitions of paintings);¹³
- organisation of visits and tours to library in multiple languages;¹⁴
- language cafés in a language that is not the national language of the library;¹⁵

⁸ Kumar, R. and Dr. Kumar, J. Enhancing Library Engagement and Awareness Through Social Media Platforms. *Journal of Information Systems Engineering and Management*. 2025, 10(30s) e-ISSN: 2468-4376 <https://jisem-journal.com/index.php/journal/issue/view/33>

⁹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/caelum/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

¹⁰ Jonaitytė, L., Štuopytė, E., Tautkevičienė, G., (2024). Academic libraries as niches of social cohesion. *AGILE consortium*. p. 11-12.

¹¹ *ibid.* p. 13-14

¹² *ibid.* p. 15-17

¹³ *ibid.* p. 18-19

¹⁴ *ibid.* p. 20-22

¹⁵ *ibid.* p. 25-26

- setup of a pleasant and calm library's environment (light, air flow, furnishings, decor);¹⁶
- organisation of volunteer groups for co-organisation of activities and for production of accessible digital books;¹⁷
- feedback by citizens through surveys, suggestion boxes, and open forums;¹⁸
- active presence in social media accounts to promote library's services and resources;¹⁹
- mobile libraries that don't expect people to come to the library but the library goes to communities (schools, daycare centers and residential areas, playgrounds, market squares, refugee camps, etc.).²⁰

Summing up this section, it is important to underline that the above-mentioned methods for audience engagement are indicative based on the literature review and previous CAELUM results and it is recommended to each partner to adjust these methods or others to the specific needs of the case study that will be implemented based on the case-specific library context.

¹⁶ Hunter C. (2021). How can academic libraries help support students' mental health?. Reflective Professional, 1. <https://doi.org/10.48525/rp-2021-id130>

¹⁷ Panteion University Library. Support for people with disabilities. Retrieved from: <https://library.panteion.gr/en/services/services-for-disabled-people/>

¹⁸ University of Oulu. Accessible library services. Retrieved from: <https://oulu.finna.fi/Feedback/Form/FeedbackService?lng=en-gb>

¹⁹ Kumar, R. and Dr. Kumar, J. Enhancing Library Engagement and Awareness Through Social Media Platforms. Journal of Information Systems Engineering and Management. 2025, 10(30s) e-ISSN: 2468-4376 <https://jisem-journal.com/index.php/journal/issue/view/33>

²⁰ Mobile Library Helsinki. Retrieved from: <https://directory.libraries.fi/helsinki/mobile-library-helsinki> & Rampen, J. (2017). Good deeds: the mobile library reaching refugees' hearts and minds. The Guardian. Retrieved from: <https://www.theguardian.com/books/2020/mar/10/echo-mobile-library-greece-refugee-camps>

6. Conclusions

This Methodology has set the context of the library's role in crisis management, by giving a definition of the notion of crisis and by identifying 5 different roles that are more relevant to specific types of crisis. Although each crisis may require different measures and practices in order to be addressed and we cannot claim that “one size fits all” approach applies here, this Methodology develops a unified approach to crisis management across different library contexts with the analysis of a number of tools, methods and practical examples that could empower libraries to undertake a vital and crucial role in the community during and after a crisis.

The effective audience engagement is paramount for libraries to maintain their relevance and support during crises and to enhance the library's visibility. Tailoring these strategies to the unique needs and contexts of each library ensures their effectiveness and sustainability. Fostering trust and familiarity with library's resources and services is crucial before a crisis emerges, as it lays the foundation for a resilient and informed community that recognises and utilises the library as a central place for reference.

The libraries' adaptive roles—ranging from providing essential services like information access and training activities to acting as community and resilience hubs during emergencies—underscore their significance in fostering societal well-being. By developing a unified approach to crisis management, libraries can enhance their preparedness and responsiveness, ensuring they continue to serve as inclusive, supportive, and essential institutions in times of uncertainty.

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